

THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS IN THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY, ITS FURTHER DEVELOPMENT

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It should be noted that over the years of independence, a stable legal framework has been created in Uzbekistan, which consolidates the primacy of private property, which is the basis of a market economy. A favorable business environment and reliable legal guarantees have been created for the rapid development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship, which is an important factor in the formation of a middle class of owners, the stable development of the country's economy, the creation of new jobs and the growth of incomes of the population.

As a result, over the past decade, the share of small businesses in the gross domestic product has increased from 31.1 percent to 52.5 percent, and the level of employment in this sector has increased from 49.7 percent to 74.5 percent compared to the total number of workers in the country . sector of the economy. More than 47 percent of the population's income comes from business income.

In accordance with the State Program "Year of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship," a set of measures has been implemented this year to create a more favorable business environment for the broad development of entrepreneurship [3].

The procedure for state registration of business entities and their connection to engineering and communication networks has been significantly simplified; this process has become more transparent. The state registration fee has been halved. The list of types of activities that small enterprises with an average annual number of employees increased to 100 people has been significantly expanded. A mechanism for large-scale involvement of small businesses in the public procurement process has been developed and implemented.

Measures have been taken to sharply reduce the intervention of government and regulatory authorities in the financial and economic activities of enterprises, to significantly expand economic freedom and the rights of business entities. The period for exemption of newly created small enterprises and microfirms from scheduled tax audits has been increased from two to three years. It was prohibited for three years to conduct tax audits for small

businesses that pay taxes and other obligatory payments on time, as well as ensure stable growth rates and profitability of production [6].

The development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan has gone through certain stages since independence to the present day. In this regard, a number of regulatory documents and legal frameworks have been created.

According to the 29th goal of the Development Strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, it is determined to create conditions for organizing business activities and forming a permanent source of income, increase the share of entrepreneurship in GDP to 80 percent and the share of exports to 60 percent [1].

Effective measures are visible to reform the national economy, liberalize foreign trade, tax and financial policies, support entrepreneurship and ensure the inviolability of private property, organize deep processing of agricultural products, and ensure rapid development of regions.

Creating economic and territorial foundations for the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship in our country is the reason for achieving positive results. As a result of the provision of large-scale tax and customs benefits for the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship, the socio-economic situation of small businesses and private entrepreneurship will significantly improve. In addition, it is fundamental in this area that the state sets such tasks as “starting from 2022, gradually introduce the procedure for entering all mandatory requirements related to entrepreneurship into a single electronic register and revise repetitive and outdated mandatory requirements” for changes [4].

Small businesses and private entrepreneurship are increasingly becoming the backbone of our economy. There is an increase in production volumes, improvement in product quality as a result of competition, and diversification of mutual economic relations.

Table 1

Share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the national economy (percentage of total volume)

Indicators	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
GDP	65,3	62,4	56,0	55,7	54,9	51,8
Industry	41,2	37,4	25,8	27,9	27,0	51,8
Construction	64,8	73,2	75,8	72,5	72,4	71,6
Job	78,0	76,3	76,2	74,5	74,4	74,4

Export	22,0	27,2	27,0	20,5	22,3	29,5
Import	53,6	56,2	61,6	51,7	48,7	49,4

The development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship in our country can be judged by their main economic indicators and their share in production in industries (Table 1) [2].

Factors influencing the further development of small business and private entrepreneurship include:

- reduction in the number of employees in large production;
- reducing the tendency of enterprises to grow;
- increasing the pace of opening new enterprises, etc.

Support for small businesses and private entrepreneurship in our country is carried out mainly in the following ways:

- further improvement of the mechanism for providing loans to small businesses and private enterprises, increasing their volume;
- creating more favorable conditions for small businesses and private entrepreneurship in terms of paying taxes and other payments and providing benefits;
- creating a more favorable business environment in our country and its regions, strengthening the priority of private property;
- attracting foreign investment in the development of small businesses;
- further simplification of procedures for creating small enterprises and registering small enterprises and entrepreneurs [5].

At the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to support small businesses and private entrepreneurship, the necessary decisions, laws, decrees and similar legal documents have been adopted and are being implemented. At the same time, in order to encourage entrepreneurship, two funds were created: a fund for the development of entrepreneurship and a fund for supporting the development of small businesses. From January 1, 2023, the value added tax rate for entrepreneurs will be reduced from the current 15 percent to 12 percent, and from July 1, 2022, the application of increased tax rates to empty buildings and unused land will be canceled, and entrepreneurs have thus been announced the repayment previously inflated debts amounting to 2 trillion [2]

In short, opening up a broad path to the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship, that is, to the development of the non-state sector, creates an opportunity to accelerate the pace of economic reforms. In our

country, many favorable opportunities are being created for the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship; we can say that both material and moral support are provided to those who are just starting to engage in entrepreneurship. At the same time, the allocation of financial resources aimed at creating a convenient financing system for entrepreneurs, for example, 20 trillion soums will be directed to small business projects, and in addition, attracting funds from international financial institutions to commercial banks is an obvious step. example. In our country, a lot of work is being done to promote the development of private entrepreneurship, create and improve its legal protection, and bring private entrepreneurship to a leading position in the country's economy.

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